

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7648499

Technical note on the climate suitability of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*

Eugenio Rossi, Caterina Campese, Malayka Picchi, Stella Papanastassiou,
Irene Pilar Muñoz Guajardo, Giuseppe Stancanelli, Andrea Maiorano

Abstract

Climate suitability analysis allows to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest. This analysis is typically based on pest ecophysiology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available. In the context of the related EFSA pest risk assessment (PRA), a climate suitability analysis was performed for *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*. The current publication includes: (i) a report on the extensive literature search conducted to retrieve data and information on the pest observed distribution and ecophysiology parameters, and on the methodology of the climate suitability analysis, (ii) an excel file including metadata on the literature analysed, (iii) an excel file including the observed distribution of the pest, (iv) maps related to the climate suitability analysis of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*, (v) a Geopackage file including the layers related to the climate suitability analysis, (vi) raster files including the output of the simulations of the physiologically based demographic modelling approach used in the PRA.

© European Food Safety Authority, 2023

Keywords: (climate suitability, pest risk assessment, pest distribution, *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*, False Codling Moth)

Suggested citation: Rossi Eugenio, Campese Caterina, Picchi Malayka, Papanastassiou Stella, Muñoz Guajardo Irene Pilar, Stancanelli Giuseppe, & Maiorano Andrea. (2023). EFSA Climate Suitability Analysis of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648499>

© European Food Safety Authority, 2023

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

EFSA may include images or other content for which it does not hold copyright. In such cases, EFSA indicates the copyright holder and users should seek permission to reproduce the content from the original source.

Table of contents

- Abstract 1
- Table of contents..... 4
- 1 Introduction 5
- 2 Note on this report 5
- 3 Methods 5
- 3.1 Systematic literature review 5
- 3.2 Document screening 7
- 3.2.1 Data extraction 7
- 4 Results 8
- 4.1 Systematic literature review 8
- 4.2 Observed distribution data 9
- 4.3 Relevant climate types 10
- 5 Content of the *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* Zenodo repository 12
- References 14

1 Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (ISPM 11, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). An extensive literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the distribution of the pest *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*. The data on distribution extracted from the literature search were also used to extract the Koppen-Geiger climate types present in the areas where *T. leucotreta* was observed.

2 Note on this report

This document includes a description of the climate suitability analysis methodology applied to *T. leucotreta*. The analysis was conducted in the context of the EFSA *Assessment of the probability of introduction of Thaumatotibia leucotreta into the European Union with import of cut roses* (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2023). For a complete description and discussion of the results of the present analysis, inserted in the framework of the pest risk assessment, please refer to the assessment cited above.

3 Methods

3.1 Systematic literature review

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *T. leucotreta*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records of the EPPO Global Database¹ and CABI database².

Table 1: List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search.

Databases	Platforms
<i>Web of Science Core Collection</i>	Web of Science
<i>Biosis</i>	
<i>CAB Abstracts</i>	
<i>Chinese Science Citation Database</i>	
<i>Current Content Connect</i>	
<i>FSTA- the food science resource</i>	
<i>Korean Journal Database</i>	
<i>Medline</i>	
<i>Russian Science Citation Index</i>	
<i>SciELO Citation Index</i>	
<i>Scopus</i>	Scopus

A combination of the scientific and international common names of the pest, retrieved from CABI and EPPO Global database (shown in Table 2), was used to interrogate the bibliographic

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/product/qc>

databases. No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, etc...) to not limit the retrieval of documents that could include information useful for the purposes of this search as secondary information, especially in the case of pest distribution.

Table 2: Taxonomy, common names, EPPO code, and main hosts of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*.

Scientific name	<i>Thaumatotibia leucotreta</i> (Meyrick)
Other scientific names	<i>Argyroploce leucotreta</i> (Meyrick) <i>Cryptophlebia leucotreta</i> (Meyrick) <i>Olethreutes leucotreta</i> (Meyrick) <i>Cryptophlebia roerigii</i> (Zacher) <i>Thaumatotibia roerigii</i> (Zacher)
International common names	palomilla de la naranja, fausse carpocapse, teigne de l'oranger, falschen Apfelwickler, citrus codling moth, orange codling moth, orange moth, false codling moth, faux carpocapse
Taxonomy	Kingdom: Animalia Phylum: Arthropoda Subphylum: Hexapoda Class: Insecta Order: Lepidoptera Family: Tortricidae
EPPO code	ARGPLE
Crop hosts	Highly polyphagous

Table 3 shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search and the number of documents obtained. Before starting the screening phase and the data extraction, all the references from WoS and Scopus were checked for duplicates.

Table 3: Search strings used to interrogate the bibliographic databases.

Platform	Set	Date of search	Query	Results
Web of Science	#1	12/05/2022	TS=(“Thaumatotibia leucotreta” OR “Argyroploce leucotreta” OR “Cryptophlebia leucotreta” OR “Cryptophlebia roerigii” OR “Olethreutes leucotreta” OR “Thaumatotibia roerigii” OR “citrus codling moth” OR “false codling moth” OR “orange codling moth” OR “orange moth” OR “faux carpocapse” OR “palomilla de la naranja” OR “fausse carpocapse” OR “teigne de l'oranger” OR “falschen Apfelwickler”)	651
Scopus	#1	12/05/2022	TITLE-ABS-KEY(“Thaumatotibia leucotreta” OR “Argyroploce leucotreta” OR “Cryptophlebia leucotreta” OR “Cryptophlebia roerigii” OR “Olethreutes leucotreta” OR “Thaumatotibia roerigii” OR “citrus codling moth” OR “false codling moth” OR “orange codling moth” OR “orange moth” OR “faux carpocapse” OR “palomilla de la naranja” OR “fausse carpocapse” OR “teigne de l'oranger” OR “falschen Apfelwickler”)	205

3.2 Document screening

Document screening followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question “Is there any information on the distribution of the pest?”.

The first step was based on titles and abstracts and the above question was applied to identify the presence of elements in the abstract and title indicating the potential availability of information on the distribution of the pest. By selecting the answer “yes”, the reference was automatically moved to the full text screening. When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening was based on the full text of the documents previously selected.

3.2.1 Data extraction

Extracted data were recorded on two files for the documents passing the full-text screening. One Excel sheet describing all the relevant information extracted, hereafter referred to as ‘Master file’ (ANNEX A), and one csv file used to record data on pest distribution (ANNEX B).

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file.

Field name	Description	Type
<i>Refid</i>	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
<i>Reference</i>	Full reference for the record	String
<i>Primary_source</i>	Source of info	String
<i>Distribution</i>	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Other</i>	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>T</i>	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>RH</i>	Presence of information on relative humidity or moisture (indicated through “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Photoperiod</i>	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through “x”). Empty means no information	Boolean

Table 4 shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the Master file, while the distribution file (Table 5) contains data on the geographical observations of the pest. When available, additional information on the organism were recorded including the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear) in the field ‘Species_status1’, and the reported persistence of the organism in the observed location (i.e., Persistent, Transient, or Unclear) in the field ‘Species_status2’. An additional table associated to the distribution table and including notes and information on specific records was also created as supporting information.

Table 5: *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
<i>Obs_ID</i>	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
<i>Continent</i>	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
<i>Country</i>	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
<i>State</i>	State where the organism observation was reported	String
<i>Observation</i>	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
<i>Admin.level</i>	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation ('location' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
<i>Admin.source</i>	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (usually FAO GAUL layer)	String
<i>Admin.code</i>	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation ('NA' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
<i>Lat</i>	Latitude of the organism observation	Double
<i>Long</i>	Longitude of the organism observation	Double
<i>Google_Earth_coord</i>	Indicates if Google Earth coordinates were used to identify the organism location, only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were already indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
<i>RefID</i>	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Error! Reference source not found.	Integer
<i>Species_status1</i>	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area of observation (i.e., Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
<i>Species_status2</i>	Classifies the organism persistence in the area of observation (i.e., Persistent, Migrant, or Unclear)	String
<i>Notes</i>	Flagged records (with 'x') include additional information saved in the support table	Boolean
<i>Uncertain</i>	Flagged records (with 'x') refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g., records from museums, interceptions, not clear information)	Boolean

Data on the observed distribution were used to extract the relevant climate types from the Köppen–Geiger climate classification as described in EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2023.

4 Results

4.1 Systematic literature review

The process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on distribution of *T. leucotreta* is summarized in the PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) in Figure 1. A total of 856 documents were retrieved from the search in scientific databases. Overall, 651 documents were found through the Web of Science platform and 205 through the SCOPUS platform. After excluding duplicates, 723 documents were assessed for the first level screening (title and abstract) and 436 documents were then selected for the second level screening (full text). A total of 261 papers were used for the data extraction from scientific databases. Out of these 261

papers, 240 included information on *T. leucotreta* distribution and 95 contained information on its ecophysiology.

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*.

4.2 Observed distribution data

Seven hundred and forty-two records of the presence of *T. leucotreta* were collected from the literature analysed. The 697 records are all available in the observation file (ANNEX B), including the uncertainty points excluded from the final maps. Additional 40 observations were included coming from the Ethiopian National Government (ANNEX C) (Kenia Plant Health Inspectorate Service (KEPHIS), 2022), and other 14 from the Kenyan National Government (ANNEX D)

(Ethiopian Agriculture Authority, 2022), for a total amount of 751 records (Figure 2). Out of these, 516 are point observations reporting specific coordinates, or relatively very small administrative units (e.g., small provinces or counties) for which coordinates from Google Earth were used. The remaining 235 records are related to larger administrative units, like regions and countries, identified with their Global Administrative Unit Layers (GAUL) code (FAO)³.

Most of the observations (59%) concentrate in the sub-Saharan Africa, especially in Ethiopia, Kenya, and South Africa. The observations recorded outside of Africa, 15 in Europe, 2 in the US, and one in New Zealand are considered interceptions, thus excluded from the analysis. Israel is the only country outside the African continent where the pest was identified and now is reported as established, especially in the Central District and the Tel Aviv District. The first identification dates to 1984 on macadamia nuts (Wysocki, 1986).

Figure 2: Observed distribution of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta*. The map on the left (1) shows point observations. The map on the right (2) shows the administrative units for the areas where point observations were not found.

4.3 Relevant climate types

Figure 3 shows the world distribution of Köppen–Geiger climate types where *T. leucotreta* was observed and that are also present in Europe. Additional results and discussion are available in the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2023).

³ <https://data.apps.fao.org/map/catalog/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/9c35ba10-5649-41c8-bdfc-eb78e9e65654>

Figure 3: Global map of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* climate matching analysis based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. Red dots indicate point observations of the pest (coordinates). Climates not present in EU are not mapped. Legend shows the lists of Köppen-Geiger climate types.

5 Content of the *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* Zenodo repository

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *T. leucotreta*, describing the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Two maps illustrate the observed distribution and results of the climate matching analysis. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2023) for an exhaustive and more comprehensive discussion of the results of the climate suitability analysis.

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf*.

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ANNEX_B_Observations.csv

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution at a global level. Both punctual locations and administrative units are included.

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ANNEX_C_Observations_Ethiopia_Gov.csv

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution received from the Ethiopian National Government.

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_ANNEX_D_Observations_Kenya_Gov.csv

The file contains the list of the organism observed distribution received from the Kenyan National Government.

Maps in .jpeg format

Maps of Climate Classification Analysis:

- *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_Observed_distribution.jpg*
- *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_Global_KG.jpg*

- *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_Europe_Africa.jpg*
- *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_Kenya_Ethiopia_SAfrica.jpg*

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_PRA.gpkg

GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_qgis_styles.zip

QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in *Thaumatotibia_leucotreta_PRA.gpkg*

pbdm_data.zip

Compressed file including the rasters with the results of the physiologically based demographic modelling approach used in the PRA

References

- Devorshak, C. (2012). Plant pest risk analysis: concepts and applications: Cabi.
- EFSA. (2010). Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. *EFSA journal*, 8(6), 1637.
- EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH), Bragard, C., Baptista, P., Chatzivassiliou, E., Di Serio, F., Gonthier, P., . . . Milonas, P. (2023). Assessment of the probability of introduction of *Thaumatotibia leucotreta* into the European Union with import of cut roses. *EFSA journal*, 21(10), 1-166. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.8107>
- Ethiopian Agriculture Authority. (2022). Rapid assessment of false codling moth (*Thaumatotibia leucotreta*) in cut flowers of roses in Ethiopia. Communication to EFSA.
- IPPC. (2013). ISPM 11: Pest risk analysis for quarantine pests. Retrieved from
- Kenia Plant Health Inspectorate Service (KEPHIS). (2022). Information on false codling moth in rose cut flowers in Kenya. Communication to EFSA.
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., & Altman, D. G. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *BMJ*, 339, b2535. doi:10.1136/bmj.b2535
- Wysocki, M. (1986). New records of lepidopterous pests of macadamia in Israel. *Phytoparasitica*, 14(2).